

Supporting Material

Expanded ligands based upon iron(II) coordination compounds of asymmetrical bis(terpyridine) domains

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Fig. S1. Base peak in the electrospray mass spectrum of **1**.

Fig. S2. Base peak in the electrospray mass spectrum of **3**.

Fig. S3. Base peak in the electrospray mass spectrum of **4**.

Fig. S4. The electrospray mass spectrum of **2**.

Fig. S5. HMQC spectrum of **1** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S6. HMBC spectrum of **1** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S7. HMQC spectrum of **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S8. HMBC spectrum of **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S9. HMQC spectrum of **4** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S10. HMBC spectrum of **4** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S11. ^1H NMR spectrum of **2** (^1H 500 MHz DMSO- d_6 , 298 K). * = residual DMSO- d_5 .

Fig. S12. HMQC spectrum of **2** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , 298 K).

Fig. S13. HMBC spectrum of **2** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 298 K).

Fig. S14. The search motif used in Conquest (version 2022.2.0) [1]. Both B and C(19) were defined as 3-coordinate; --- = any bond type; normalized H coordinates were applied. The H...B contact was defined as $\leq$ sum of the van der Waals radii.

Fig. S15. The $[M+H]^+$ and $[M+Na]^+$ peaks in the high resolution electrospray mass spectrum of **5**. Top, experimental; bottom, simulated.

Fig. S16. The $[M+2H]^{2+}$ and $[M+H]^+$ peaks in the high resolution electrospray mass spectrum of **6**. Top, experimental; bottom, simulated.

Fig. S17. HMQC spectrum of **5** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Fig. S18. HMBC spectrum of **5** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Fig. S19. HMQC spectrum of **6** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Fig. S20. HMBC spectrum of **6** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Fig. S21. The $[M]^{2+}$ peak in the high resolution electrospray mass spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{5})_2][\text{NO}_3]_2$: top, experimental spectrum; bottom, simulated spectrum.

Fig. S22. The $[M]^{2+}$ peak in the high resolution electrospray mass spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{6})_2][\text{BF}_4]_2$: top, experimental spectrum; bottom, simulated spectrum.

Fig. S23. HMQC spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{5})]_2[\text{NO}_3]_2$ (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CD_3CN , 298 K).

Fig. S24. HMBC spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{5})]_2[\text{NO}_3]_2$ (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CD_3CN , 298 K).

Fig. S25. HMQC spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{6})_2][\text{BF}_4]_2$ (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CD_3CN , 298 K). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ signal at δ 118.26 ppm arises from CD_3CN .

Fig. S26. HMBC spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\mathbf{6})_2][\text{BF}_4]_2$ (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CD_3CN , 298 K). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ signal at δ 118.26 ppm arises from CD_3CN .

Fig. S27. Comparison of the aromatic regions of the ¹H NMR spectra (500 MHz, 298 K) of (a) compound **5** in CDCl₃, and (b) [Fe(**5**)₂][NO₃]₂ in CD₃CN. The effect of coordination on the chemical shifts of the signals for protons H^{A6}, H^{B3} and H^{C6} (see Scheme 5 for atom labels) is highlighted.

Reference

1. Bruno, I.J.; Cole, J.C.; Edgington, P.R.; Kessler, M.; Macrae, C.F.; McCabe, P.; Pearson, J.; Taylor, R. New software for searching the Cambridge Structural Database and visualising crystal structures. *Acta Cryst.* **2002**, *B58*, 389-397. doi: 10.1107/S0108768102003324